

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

FACTORS AFFECTING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF ARMENIAN AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS

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ABSTRACT

The competitiveness of agricultural products is important both from the point of view of its representation in foreign markets and the growth of export volumes, as well as from the point of competition with imported products in the domestic market. The export of agricultural products from Armenia has been increasing with high rates in recent years, whereas the output in agricultural sector keeps decreasing. This raises the necessity to analyse the factors affecting the agricultural export and output, with the aim of revealing the main macroeconomic factors affecting competitiveness of Armenian agricultural products. The study was done using regression analysis based on quarterly data. The macroeconomic factors affecting agriculture were grouped in 4 categories: price factors, supply factor, demand factors and government policy factors. The results show that the competitiveness of agricultural export, as well as agricultural output is mostly affected by price factors.

Keywords: agriculture, competitiveness, agricultural export, agricultural policy, exchange rate.

Introduction

A fundamental role in professional literature on international trade and competitiveness have A. Smith's theory about absolute advantages, as well as D. Ricardo's theories of relative advantage, that identify a number of factors determining the effectiveness of international trade, including resources spent on production, availability of production factors, opportunity costs, etc. In later theories, national competitiveness is presented as the result of innovative activities to gain or maintain an advantageous position over other countries in key areas. According to the famous economist P. Krugman, another key factor for gaining and maintaining a favourable position in international markets is state trade policy [6].

The proposed methodologies for assessing competitiveness in the professional literature mainly come down to the study of product export and import ratios, as well as the dynamics of product export volumes in the markets of partner countries. In the case of agricultural products, the dynamics of the export and import ratios, as well as the weights of their volumes in relation to the GDPs of the producing and importing countries, are also important [2, 10]. Thus, from the point of view of the competitiveness of agricultural products, it is also important to study the factors influencing its export volumes and evaluate the extent and directions of their influence.

Among the factors affecting the international trade of agricultural products, the following are distinguished in the professional literature [10].

1. price factors that explain the price of a product in international markets and its relative position in comparison with the products of competing countries,

2. Income and population growth in partner countries, leading to increased export volumes,

3. government policy intervention to promote exports, which may include.

a. trade policy,

b. promotion of domestic agriculture through subsidies and other types of support,

c. State regulatory costs (related to food safety measures),

d. other state support. For example, building and upgrading infrastructure for agricultural production,

4. Supply factors, such as weather conditions, access to irrigation, qualitative and quantitative characteristics of the labor force, etc.

The price factors of agricultural products, having significant impact on export volumes, are a subject for a separate analysis. In particular, the price of agricultural products in international markets is determined by the following factors.

1. The price of the product at the time of crossing the border, which is affected by the level of wages in the domestic market, as well as labor productivity in the agricultural sector, technological saturation, weather conditions and other factors,

2. Travel expenses to the destination, which can be a significant obstacle in the case of countries like RA,

3. Customs duties, import taxes and other mandatory charges in the importing country,

4. Exchange rate.

In professional literature, there is also a strong emphasis on actual developments. There are a number of empirical studies on the export factors of agricultural products.

Empirical researches are mainly based on the so-called "gravity models", which was first used in the middle of the 20th century [11] and has been considerably developed and theorized by many authors over the decades [7]. That kind of models are based on the idea that the volume of foreign trade and its change are proportional to the volume of the economies of the trading countries, their changes, as well as the trade imperfections between the two countries (for example, tariff and non-tariff restrictions).

Based on the data of developing countries (Iran, India, Malaysia, Pakistan, Thailand, Turkey, Brazil, Indonesia, Kenya, Venezuela, Tunisia, Romania), the empirical analysis carried out using the aforementioned methods allowed to find a significant and positive relationship between GDP per capita in the importing country and the volume of import of agricultural products. Meanwhile, the growth of per capita GDP of a developing country that exports agricultural products has a negative effect on export volumes, which means that economic development is accompanied by a slowdown in the export of agricultural products. As for the exchange rate, empirical analysis has shown that the increase in exchange rate volatility has a negative impact on international trade in agricultural products, which is explained by the increase in uncertainty under exchange rate volatility [5].

Another empirical analysis, conducted using Turkey's quarterly data on 1994-2012 years, data showed that the most important factors from the point of view of international trade of agricultural products are real exchange rate, real GDP and prices of agricultural products. The authors of the study also state that the state policy implemented in the sector and the introduction of new technologies that increase productivity have a positive effect on the trade balance of agricultural products [9].

Empirical analyses were also conducted on the example of the Nigerian economy using regression models. In this case, domestic production growth, production prices, exchange rate, domestic consumption and interest rate were underlined as factors having a significant impact on the export of agricultural products [1].

Some authors have studied the factors influencing the export of individual agricultural products. In this context, Gbetkom and Khan studied the factors affecting the export of cocoa, coffee and bananas using the data of Cameroon and revealed that the most significant effects on export levels of mentioned products have relative price changes in favour of the Cameroonian economy, international communication channels (improvement of the road network) as well as increases in loans

to producers. Moreover, the authors used the increase in the length of roads, including both paved and unpaved roads, as an indicator of the improvement of the road network. A positive relationship was also revealed with factors such as weather conditions (rainfall) and government policy measures [3].

In order to analyse factors affecting exports of around 10 South African agricultural products (the largest exports by volume), the authors included a wider range of factors in the models, including the GDP index in the producing and importing countries, the physical distance between economies, and the levels of development (difference in GDP per capita), the case of having a common border and being in economic unions, etc. At the same time, the research was carried out separately for the 10 agricultural products with the largest export volumes. The results showed that depending on the type of product, the factors explaining export volumes differ. However, the most significant factors for most products were population growth, as well as GDP growth in South Africa and partner countries [4].

Research methodology

Based on the literature review, the "gravity models" methodology was chosen in this study to analyse the export trends of Armenian agricultural products. In other words, it was studied to what extent the export volumes of agricultural products are correlated with the size of the economies of RA and partner countries and their changes, as well as how other macroeconomic factors are affecting the export dynamics of agricultural products. For that reason, all the macroeconomic factors affecting agricultural exports are grouped in the following categories:

- Price factors
- Supply factors
- Demand factors
- Government policy

In order to evaluate the effects of the mentioned factors, the historical trends of export and import of agricultural products were first studied in recent years. Estimation was performed using regression equations.

Analysis

Developments in the field of agriculture in recent years are quite noteworthy. Apart from 2010, high growths were recorded in the agricultural sector during 2001-2015, on average around 8.3%, as a result of which in 2015 the real volume of agricultural production was about 2.5 times greater than in 2000. Then, between 2016 and 2021, agriculture sector declined at an average annual rate of around 4.5%.

Figure 1. Volumes of agricultural products in 2000-2021

Source: RA Statistical Committee, authors' calculations

Figure 2. Agricultural product export trends and share of agriculture in GDP, %

The weight of agriculture in the GDP has significantly decreased in the last ten years, reaching 11.3% compared to 17.9% in 2012. At the same time, the volume of export of agricultural products has increased. In 2021 the agricultural exports reached to 2.1% as a share of GDP and 9.7% as a share of total exports, compared to 0.6% and 4.9% respectively in 2012. Such dynamics indicate that the production of agricultural products has grown at a slower rate compared to the RA economy, but the exported part has increased in its structure. This is also evidenced by the fact that the ratio of the export

volume of agricultural products to the output volume of the sector has increased significantly in recent years (see Figure 3). Along with that, the volumes of import of agricultural products also increased and the net export of these products remained in the negative range. It means that although the growth of export of agricultural products significantly exceeds the growth of the main macroeconomic indicators of RA, its competitiveness with respect to imported products has not enough improved.

Figure 3. The share of export of agricultural products to the output of agriculture, %
Source: RA Statistical Committee, authors' calculations

Figure 4. Export and import of agricultural products

In order to make judgments about the competitiveness of products in foreign markets, firstly it is necessary to study the geography of export of agricultural products. According to statistical data, the main export direction of RA agricultural products has historically been the Russian Federation, which accounts for more

than 80% of exports from RA. Moreover, this weight has increased in recent years, approaching 90%. Among other countries, Iraq, Kuwait, and Georgia have a significant weight, to which exports fluctuated on average within 2.4, 0.7 and 4.4 percent respectively during 2015-2021.

Table 1.

Export directions of agricultural products, % of total exports							
Countries	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Russia	79.5	81.5	72.7	81.2	84.1	89.2	87.8
Iraq	1.6	0.6	4.7	0.8	2.8	2.2	4.2
Kuwait	0.0	0.4	0.1	0.2	0.4	1.4	2.1
Georgia	11.4	6.1	4.8	2.9	2.6	1.3	1.8
Suriname	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0
USA	0.8	0.4	0.5	0.9	1.0	0.8	0.8
Qatar	0.0	0.0	1.2	0.7	1.0	2.3	0.6
Lebanon	1.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.8	0.4
Jordan	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.5	0.4	0.3
Belarus	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.5	0.2
France	0.0	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.1
UAE	0.1	0.6	1.0	1.1	0.7	0.3	0.1
Iran	3.4	9.3	14.1	11.0	5.6	0.1	0.1

Source: RA SRC customs statistics, authors' calculations

It is noteworthy that exports to the Islamic Republic of Iran had a significant weight in 2016-2018, averaging around 11.5%, but sharply decreased in 2020-2021, reaching 0.1%

Given the aforementioned statistics, the study of the dynamics of the export of agricultural products to the Russian market will be enough to be able to gain

insight into the change in the competitiveness of the whole agricultural export from Armenia. The basic rationale for judging changes in competitiveness based on export volumes is that if export volume increases faster than the macro indicators in foreign market, that indicates that country's competitiveness has increased.

Figure 5: Nominal volume index (ex-pressed in USD), 2000 = 100

Source: RA Statistical Committee, RF Federal Statistical Service, authors' calculations

Figure 5 shows the dollar indices of agricultural exports, total exports of RA and nominal GDP of the Russian Federation. It can be seen from the chart that the export volumes of agricultural products from RA to the Russian Federation increased by about 120 times from 2000 to 2021, while the economy of the Russian Federation increased by about 6.4 times, and the total export from RA increased by about 10 times.

During the last 10 years, the fast growth of agricultural export volume has been maintained. Thus, the growth during 2012-2021 was about 4.4 times, while the total export from RA to the Russian Federation increased only 2.2 times, and the nominal GDP of the Russian Federation expressed in US dollars decreased by about 19%. The rapid growth rate of export of agricultural products surely is a positive phenomenon and

can be considered as an indicator of increasing competitiveness. However, it is also necessary to identify the main factors that contributed to the increase in the competitiveness of RA products in the main export market, so that it is possible to ensure the policy aimed at further increasing competitiveness.

Assessment of the impact of macroeconomic factors on the export of agricultural products

Competitiveness is affected by many factors, which are discussed in more detail in the literature review section. In this study, an assessment of the impact of a number of factors on the production and export of agricultural products was carried out, with the assumption that the factors contributing to the growth of export are also factors that increase competitiveness of agricultural products.

The selection of macroeconomic factors is based on the analysis of academic literature. In particular, the factors that have a significant impact on export volumes were identified and their role in export growth was assessed. The selected factors can be grouped as follows

- **Price factors**, which affect the price competitiveness of exported goods. Such factors are the exchange rate, sale prices of agricultural products in RA and RF,
- **Supply factors**, that indicate production constraints. The growth of the RA GDP, the increase in the output of agricultural products and the added value were used as supply factors in the research,
- **Demand factors**, that show the change in the situation in the export market, in this case the Russian market,
- **Government policy measures**, that shows to what extent the measures implemented by the government have affected the volume of export of agricultural products. This group of factors include state budget expenditures in the field of agriculture and other support measures.

In order to evaluate the impact of the mentioned factors, separate two-dimensional regression equations were built, so that it is possible to consider the impact and significance of each of the indicators in the production and export of agricultural products. The summary results of the regression equation are presented in Tables 2 and 3.

Quarterly time series were used to assess relationships between indicators. The time range of the variables were taken depending on the availability of data. For example, the information on loans in the agricultural sector has been available since 2014, therefore the impact was evaluated in those years, and, the impact of the growth indicators of the Russian Federation's GDP was evaluated using data from 2001-2021.

The stationarity of the variables was evaluated using statistical tests (Augmented Dickey-Fuller, Phillips-Perron, KPSS), which showed that the indicators are not stationary in levels. Therefore, in the regression analysis, the year-on-year growth rates were used.

Specifically, the following factors have been considered as factors affecting the export of agricultural products and the added value of the agricultural sector:

- Armenian GDP growth
- Loans to agricultural sector
- Government expenditure in the field of agriculture
- Growth of the real GDP of the Russian Federation
- Transportation costs
- Prices of agricultural products in RA (including prices of individual products of plant and animal origin)
 - Prices of agricultural products in the Russian Federation (including prices of individual plant and animal products)
 - The real effective exchange rate
 - Nominal effective exchange rate
 - The nominal exchange rate of the Armenian dram against the US dollar
 - The nominal exchange rate of the Armenian dram against the Russian ruble

Table 2 presents the results of the assessment of the effects of the aforementioned factors on the export volumes of agricultural products of RA. However, in the table included only those factors, which effects on agricultural exports is statistically significant. In other words, within the framework of the research, the effects of all indicators on export volumes were evaluated, but for most of the correlation was not significant. The estimation was performed up to 8 lags for each variable.

Table 2.

Summary of the assessment of the effects of individual factors on the export volume of agricultural products

Variable	Impact coefficient	Lag of influence	t-statistics	Significance (p-value)	R ²	Time period for estimation
Government expenditure in the field of agriculture	-0.209	-2	-2.108	0.040	0.082	2009-2021
AMD to RUB exchange rate	-0.591	0	-1.926	0.059	0.062	2008-2021
Increase in the prices of plant-based products in RF	0.690	0	2.115	0.040	0.096	2011-2021
Transportation costs	-1.625	0	-2.710	0.009	0.120	2008-2021

A significant impact on the volume of export of agricultural products was revealed in terms of some of the considered factors, that are presented in Table 2. However, in addition to being significant, the size and sign of the coefficients are also important. Thus, for example, the impact of government support programs in

the field of agriculture on the export of agricultural products is negative, which means that the increase in expenditures of the state budget in this field leads to a decrease in the export of agricultural products after two quarters. This result can be explained by the fact that

the increase in spending in the agricultural sector occurred in unfavourable years when the government provided compensation to farmers for crop losses due to weather or other problems. The rest of the factors presented in Table 2 have the more logical interconnections and have a significant impact on the export of agricultural products. As mentioned, the presented coefficients were obtained as a result of two-dimensional regressions, and to check the unbiasedness of the coefficients, a multivariate regression equation was created, where the effects of the mentioned factors on the export of agricultural products were estimated in one equation in the following way:

$$Exp_t^{agr} = \beta_1 GDP_t^{Rus} + \beta_2 P_t^{Rus} + \beta_3 Tr_t + \beta_4 G_{t-2}^{agr} + \beta_5 RUB_t + \varepsilon$$

$$Exp_t^{agr} = 2.22 * GDP_t^{Rus} + 0.52 * P_t^{Rus} - 1.728 * Tr_t - 0.01 * G_{t-2}^{agr} - 0.74 * RUB_t$$

(3.394)*** (2.072)*** (-3.142)*** (-0.108) (-2.777)**

The obtained results are quite close to the individual estimates of the factors, which indicates that the coefficients obtained by bivariate regression are stable. However, the extent and significance of the impact of some important factors varies. In particular, in the case of evaluating through bivariate regression, it turns out that the increase in the government expenses in agricultural sector has a negative effect on the volume of product exports. Meanwhile, when other factors explaining the growth of agricultural output are included in the equation, the impact of budget expenditures becomes insignificant. From this it can be concluded that the increase of state budget expenses does not have a significant effect on the growth of agricultural exports, therefore it is also not significant from the point of view of competitiveness.

Another indicator, that has different coefficients in bivariate and multivariate regression, is the growth of the real GDP of the Russian Federation. In the case of bivariate regression, it does not have a significant impact on the growth of export of agricultural products. This may be due to the fact that the real GDP of the Russian Federation explains a very small part of the variation in the export of agricultural products, and without the inclusion of other factors, the model fails to reveal the existing relationship. However, in the case of adding additional factors, the influence of the real GDP of the Russia becomes significant, having a significantly high coefficient. It is logical, taking into account the size of the Russian economy compared to the volume of export of agricultural products of the Republic of Armenia

In general, we can note that there are not many factors that have a significant impact on the export of agricultural products. Two of them, the growth of the real GDP of Russia and the prices in foreign market should be considered as exogenous factors, while the prices of transportation in Armenia and the exchange rate of the AMD against RUB are to some extent influenced by state policy and have a significant impact on

where, Exp_t^{agr} is the increase in the volume of export of agricultural products, GDP_t^{Rus} The real growth of the Russian GDP is, P_t^{Rus} The increase in the prices of vegetable products in the Russian Federation, Tr_t is the transportation costs, G_{t-2}^{agr} budget expenditures on agriculture sector in Armenia ("t-2" means that expenditures affect after two quarters) and RUB_t is the change in the exchange rate of the AMD against the RUB (increase means appreciation): $\beta_1 - \beta_5$ coefficients that characterize the size and direction of the influence of the factors included in the equation on the dependent variable (Exp_t^{agr}).

The above formula will look like this after estimation using least squares method:

the agricultural export. Therefore, in order to increase competitiveness, it is necessary to make efforts to improve these factors

Assessment of the impact of macroeconomic factors on the agricultural output

For a more comprehensive analysis of the factors affecting agriculture, this study also assesses the effects of various factors on the value added of agriculture. As can be seen from the data in Figure 1, the agricultural sector has been in continuous decline in recent years, and it is unnecessary to identify the macroeconomic factors that in some extent can explain this decline.

With that aim, the same factors that was used to analyse the agricultural export dynamics, also were used for agricultural output analysis. Table 3 presents the results of the assessment of the factors that have a significant impact on the dynamics in the agricultural sector. The effects of the remaining factors were also assessed, but no significant relationship was identified under any specification¹.

According to the estimation results, the increase of the RA GDP, the increase in the prices of agricultural products in the RA, the increase in the prices of agricultural products in the Russian Federation, and the increase in government expenditures in the field of agriculture have a significant impact on the added value of the agricultural sector. It should be noted that the influence of government spending in the agricultural sector in this case also has a negative sign. However, as in the previous case, the coefficient and significance of the effect of government spending is not maintained in the case of adding other variables to the model. It is noteworthy that the increase in the prices of agricultural products of Russia has a significant impact on both agricultural production and export indicators.

Table 3.

Summary of the assessment of the effects of macroeconomic factors on the volumes of agricultural output

¹ The evaluations carried out under conditions of different transformations of time series, as well as different lags.

Variable	Impact coefficient	Lag of influence	t-statistics	Significance (p-value)	R ²	Time period for estimation
Real GDP growth in Armenia	0.556	0	4.367	0.000	0.187	2001-2021
Real GDP growth in Russia	0.664	0	2.783	0.007	0.085	2001-2021
Government expenditure in the field of agriculture	-0.052	-3	-2.082	0.043	0.072	2009-2021
The increase in prices of agricultural products	0.379	-1	4.124	0.000	0.168	2001-2021
Increase in prices of agricultural products in Russia	0.266	-2	1.855	0.070	0.076	2011-2021

Conclusions

To sum up, we can note that in the conditions of the continuous decrease in the volume of the agricultural sector in recent years, a significant increase in the export of agricultural products was recorded, mainly to the Russian market. At the same time, the export growth rate has significantly exceeded the growth rate of the Russian economy. The agricultural exports/output ratio has significantly increased. At the same time, the volumes of import of agricultural products also increased, as a result of which the volume of net exports remained almost at the same level, on average around -200 to -300 million US dollars. It means that although the competitiveness of products has increased in foreign markets, it still does not succeed in crowding out imported products in the domestic market.

Among the macroeconomic factors, the change in prices of agricultural products is essential for both export and output volumes. Therefore, it can be concluded that the price factors are of greater importance for the development of agriculture, which should be the basis for the development of efficient state agricultural policy measures. We can also highlight the importance of freight costs for product export, as well as the significant impact of the AMD exchange rate against the RUB. These factors, compared to other macroeconomic factors, have a greater impact on the competitiveness of agricultural products, and therefore on export volumes, which means that state policy measures should include provisions aimed at improving these factors. Of course, the exchange rate is not in direct influence of government policy, however, other price factors like transportation costs can be affected by various policy tools (for example by subsidies), increasing the competitiveness of agricultural products.

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